

The Violence of the Visible

Figures that Survive, Gazes that Remake the World

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Abstract

This article advances three theoretical proposals that unsettle the traditional notions of representation in Western art and aesthetics, engaging the work of Jean-François Lyotard, Gilles Deleuze, Aby Warburg, Georges Didi-Huberman, and Luis Puelles. Each proposal foregrounds the need to reconceive artistic representation in terms of singularity, difference, immanent forces, psychism, and the spectator's active co-participation. Taken together, they provide a deeper understanding of contemporary aesthetics and its resistance to homogenizing narratives.

Keywords: representation, figurality, *pathosformel*, *Nachleben*, co-creation.

1. On Forms and Figures: Lyotard's and Deleuze's Transgression of Traditional Structures of Discourse and Representation

The connections between forms and figures have been extensively examined by Jean-François Lyotard and Gilles Deleuze. Both thinkers approach aesthetics and representation through conceptual trajectories that unsettle the traditional conventions of discourse and figuration. In this section, I analyse their respective perspectives as articulated in *Discours, figure* (Lyotard, 1971) and *Logique de la sensation* (Deleuze, 2002), highlighting points of convergence and divergence in their treatments of the figural and the discursive.

Jean-François Lyotard, in *Discours, figure*, introduces the concept of the figural as a dimension that exceeds the constraints of structuralist discourse. For Lyotard, discourse is a closed system of relations that subsumes objects under a fixed set of rules. This system, by converting reality into a series of invariants, forfeits the density and particularity of the desiring object. The figural, by contrast, represents the resistance to this subsumption, introducing a negativity that cannot be fully absorbed by discourse. To interact with an object is already to render it a sign. Discursive systems invariably fail to transmit an external correlate in full, precisely because opacity is constitutive both of communication and of external objects themselves. Language cannot integrate an external correlate into its structure without modifying it—revealing one face while concealing others. As Lyotard famously writes: « *L'opacité est dans l'objet, non dans le mot, ni dans sa distance à l'objet. Les mots ne sont pas des signes, mais dès qu'il y a un mot, l'objet désigné devient signe* » (Lyotard, 1971, p. 82).

The word as such, as sign, opens onto a value that transcends mere signalling (understood as the simple identification of a meaning through a signifier). The word, in its graphic form, is something visible; and it is this material organisation of signs to which Lyotard dedicates numerous analyses. In this context, figures are the effects produced by the materiality of the sign—both sonic and graphic. Deleuze, in conceptual consonance with Lyotard, articulated this with exceptional acuity: « *effets du signifiant lui-même, les*

éléments formels du signifiant déterminé par rapport à une substance phonique à laquelle l'écriture même confère un privilège secret» (Deleuze & Guattari, 1980, p. 288).

Within Lyotard's work, forms and figures therefore become interwoven concepts in artistic representation. The figure-image marks the blurring of the distinctive lines of representation: these lines—discursive in that they attempt to render a correlate clearly and distinctly—are distorted, multiplied, or recomposed. They generate a disorder of forms. The body affected by the figure-image appears partially to fade, yet remains recognisable; the represented object is still visible, but simultaneously melts into the surrounding space, yielding an indeterminate appearance.

The form-figure refers to a plastic space traversed by primary processes—forces that operate independently of figurative representation. Because the represented object is suspended in its unity, the form-figure becomes the visible materialisation of the processes that traverse an artwork. The matrix-figure, in turn, denotes the underlying structure that organises forms and figures across the representational surface. Lyotard underscores the importance of these three dimensions of the figural in configuring aesthetic experience. Each constitutes a mode of resistance to discursive subsumption, rendering visible the density and particularity of desire in the artwork. This resistance is fundamental to Lyotard's aesthetics, centred on the capacity of art to destabilise fixed structures of discourse and representation.

Gilles Deleuze, for his part, approaches representation and form from a different yet complementary angle in *Logique de la sensation* (Deleuze, 2002). Deleuze focuses on how sensory and perceptual forces shape aesthetic experience. For him, figures are not mere representations of an external reality, but manifestations of forces operating within the perceptual field. These forces shape the way we experience art, rendering visible the intensity and internal dynamics of figural events. The figural is not a meaningless disruption of force but the presence of forces that dissipate discursive organisation:

« C'est comme si la main prenait une indépendance, et passait au service d'autres forces, traçant des marques qui ne dépendent plus de notre volonté ni de notre vue. Ces marques manuelles presque aveugles témoignent donc de l'intrusion d'un autre monde dans le monde visuel de la figuration. Elles soustraient pour une part le tableau à l'organisation optique qui régnait déjà sur lui, et le rendait d'avance figurative » (Deleuze, 2002, p. 94).

Deleuze also interrogates the relation between the figurative and the abstract, suggesting that both dimensions are intrinsically entangled in the production of meaning. Figures emerge from a process of “making visible” that challenges the stability of signs and representation. This resonates with Lyotard's claim that the figural introduces irregularities into discourse, yet Deleuze emphasises the immanent sensory and perceptual forces that generate these irregularities.

Despite their methodological and conceptual differences, Lyotard and Deleuze share a commitment to challenging the fixed structures of discourse and representation. Both regard art and aesthetics as domains of resistance against homogenisation and subsumption of difference. Lyotard stresses the need to preserve the singularity and density of desire, while Deleuze foregrounds the immanent forces shaping aesthetic perception. Their divergence lies partly in how they conceptualise these forces and figures.

Lyotard focuses on the negativity and dislocation that the figural introduces into discourse, whereas Deleuze emphasises the positivity of sensory forces configuring perception. This distinction reflects their theoretical influences: Lyotard's engagement with phenomenology and psychoanalysis contrasts with Deleuze's philosophy of immanence and vitalism. Lyotard conceives discourse and the figural by revising the structuralist model of language. “Discourse” refers to a closed system of relations that subsumes an object under

a fixed set of rules. Meaning arises from the interplay of oppositions among coexisting terms. Subsuming a correlate under an invariant relation of signifiers produces discursive meaning. The figural emerges when the negativity repressed within discourse asserts itself—a negativity not of the same nature as linguistic negativity. Lyotard thus underlines the limits of linguistic signification and its radical difference from non-linguistic signification. Central to his conception is the idea that the disturbance of invariant intervals between terms is intranslatable into the terms and logic of discourse. The figural decomposes language into forms (visual and linguistic) that fall short of discursive comprehension.

Lyotard's view of representation centres on the tension between desire and discursive structure. Desire, in his framework, is a disruptive force that destabilises fixed structures of language and representation. This dislocation becomes visible in the artwork, where the figural acts as a force that perturbs discursive regularity, introducing elements that cannot be fully assimilated by linguistic structure.

The relations between forms and figures in Lyotard and Deleuze thus offer a rich conceptual matrix for understanding contemporary aesthetics. Both thinkers challenge traditional structures of discourse and representation and propose an aesthetics that valorises singularity, difference, and the immanent forces of perception. Through their respective explorations of the figural and the sensorial, Lyotard and Deleuze invite us to rethink the role of art and aesthetics in the production of meaning and cultural resistance. Their reflections foreground the need for an aesthetics that refuses the demands of homogeneous discourse and celebrates instead the multiplicity and irreducibility of sensory and figural experience.

At this juncture, it is crucial to highlight that the figural, by introducing irregularities and dislocations into discourse, also destabilises temporal linearity. This rupture with linear temporality enables an aesthetic experience in which past, present, and future intertwine, creating a spatiotemporal field where figures emerge and are continuously transformed. Deleuze's notion of becoming already intimates such dynamic temporality, but it is fruitful to deepen the analysis of how becoming affects aesthetic experience and artistic interpretation.

Another relevant consideration concerns the relation between materiality and the figural. While Lyotard emphasises the negativity and resistance of the figural to discourse, it is equally important to examine how such resistance manifests in the materiality of artworks. Texture, colour, and physical form may be understood as figural-material elements that resist discursive subsumption. In the plastic arts, for instance, the brushstroke, the roughness of canvas, or the three-dimensionality of sculpture introduce sensory resistances that compel a more immediate interaction with the artwork.

In the digital era, the relation between forms and figures acquires new dimensions through technology. Digital tools allow for the creation and manipulation of forms and figures in ways that challenge traditional categories of representation. Augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and emerging technologies generate novel possibilities for aesthetic experimentation. These technologies not only multiply the operations of the figural but also introduce new modes of immanence and becoming within aesthetic experience. Digital artworks, with their transformative capacities and interactivity, may be seen as contemporary manifestations of Lyotard's and Deleuze's ideas, where forces and figures unfold within hybrid realities.

A further link between Lyotard and Deleuze lies in the centrality of the body to aesthetic experience. The figural, with its destabilising force, acts directly upon the embodied perception of the spectator. The artwork, in its figural dimension, is not merely an object of visual contemplation but a multisensory event that engages the body in its entirety. This

approach resonates with phenomenological theories emphasising corporeality as the ground of aesthetic experience. The artwork is thus not only a representation but a lived event, where forms and figures interact with the spectator in an immediate and visceral register.

Finally, the political implications of the figural must be acknowledged. Both Lyotard and Deleuze suggest that the destabilisation of discourse and the introduction of immanent forces possess a subversive dimension. This subversion challenges not only traditional aesthetic structures but also the sociopolitical norms that sustain them. The resistance of the figural to discourse may therefore be understood as a resistance to dominant and homogenising narratives, opening space for plurality and difference. In this sense, figural aesthetics holds not only artistic significance but profound implications for public life and struggles for justice.

These additional reflections enrich the dialogue between Lyotard and Deleuze, situating their ideas within a broader context and opening new avenues for contemporary aesthetic theory. By considering temporality, materiality, technology, corporeality, and politics, we gain a deeper appreciation of the complexity and depth of the relations between forms and figures in artistic representation.

2. Beyond Mere Representation: The Survival of Images in Didi-Huberman through the Thought of Aby Warburg

Images are not simply fixed representations of an external world; they also endure dynamically in time and are capable of evoking affect. This is precisely what emerges from the work of Aby Warburg and Georges Didi-Huberman. Each offers a particular and complementary vision of how images not only represent reality but also function as vehicles of affects and cultural memories, thereby foregrounding the profound bond between art and human emotion. In what follows, I draw on *L'Image survivante. Histoire de l'art et temps des fantômes selon Aby Warburg* (Didi-Huberman, 2002), *El renacimiento del paganismo* (Warburg, 2005), *Ante el tiempo* (Didi-Huberman, 2006) y *L'Atlas Mnémosyne* (Didi-Huberman, 2023).

Warburg introduced the term *Pathosformel* to describe the way in which certain visual formulas and expressive gestures are transmitted across time, encapsulating intense emotions and affective states (Warburg, 2005). These formulas do not merely reproduce the external form of things; they render visible the emotional state of the human psyche. Warburg conceives such images as « *fossiles en mouvement [...] qui combinent l'énergie présente du geste avec l'énergie ancienne de la mémoire [...] et la survivance d'un éternel retour* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 339), thus enabling an understanding of history that exceeds a simple chronology of events. Images are therefore « *plastiques en raison de leur capacité de survie, c'est-à-dire dans leur relation avec le temps des fantômes [...] et au temps des corps* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 161). The notion of *Pathosformel* explains the persistence of certain gestures and emotional expressions in artistic representation over time: « *formule et pathos, schéma abstrait et représentation tactile* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 136).

These gestures, which initially appeared in classical antiquity, re-emerged in the Renaissance and have continued to be re-activated in subsequent cultures (Warburg, 2005). Warburg observed that these affective formulas were not merely aesthetic motifs; they functioned as bridges between past and present.

Drawing inspiration from Warburg, Didi-Huberman articulates a conceptual triad: the phantom-image, the pathos-image, and the symptom-image (Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006).

The phantom-image anachronises time, allowing the past to survive in the present in a hybrid, sedimented manner:

« *il dément violemment l'évidence du Zeitgeist, cet "esprit du temps" sur lequel la définition des styles artistiques est si souvent basée [...] l'origine forme donc une temporalité impure d'hybridations et de sédiments [...] la survie ouvre une brèche dans les modèles habituels de l'évolution; il trouve des paradoxes, des ironies de toutes sortes et des changements non rectilignes* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, pp. 87–89).

The phantom-image is not a mere reproduction of the past but a living presence that interacts with the present, generating a temporality in which different epochs overlap and enter into dialogue. It allows the past to survive in the present in a way that directly challenges linear time, in accordance with the Warburgian notion of *Nachleben*, where images act as bearers of cultural and emotional memory (Warburg, 2005; Didi-Huberman, 2002).

The pathos-image adds a psychic dimension to this temporality, suggesting that every *Nachleben* is also a psychic time, legible through the affective states transmitted by images (Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006). This becomes particularly evident in what we might call the “spectral art” of Henri Michaux, where the resonance with Warburg’s categories is striking. Michaux’s explorations of the depths of the unconscious and his spectral representations produce works that can be interpreted in the light of Warburgian and Didi-Hubermanian concepts.

Michaux’s spectres are visual manifestations of inner states—phantoms of the unconscious that emerge as visible symptoms in his art. His works may thus be understood as phantom-images, insofar as they evoke intangible, ethereal presences; as pathos-images, inasmuch as they express emotional intensity and existential anguish; and finally as symptom-images, since they disclose the discontinuous, fragmented temporality of human experience. The link between Warburg and Michaux is deepened in the idea that art can reveal the fractures and discontinuities of both history and psyche. Michaux’s spectral creations align with Didi-Huberman’s notion of “impure time,” showing how images encapsulate and transmit the complexity and multiplicity of being (Didi-Huberman, 2006). In this sense, Michaux’s work not only complements Warburg’s theory but extends it, providing a tangible instance of how images can function as symptoms, rendering visible the hidden depths of the unconscious and the ruptures of historical time.

Warburg and Didi-Huberman also share a sustained interest in montage as a method for revealing anachronistic temporalities. Warburg’s arrangement of images from different epochs on panels exemplifies how montage can disclose underlying connections between historically distant moments (Warburg, 2005; Didi-Huberman, 2023). Didi-Huberman takes up this idea and argues that montage grants access to a form of knowledge that cannot be attained through linear narrative alone. Rather than following a strict chronology, montage reveals resonances and echoes between disparate times and spaces, offering a richer and more complex vision of history (Didi-Huberman, 2006, 2023).

The notion of the symptom-image is developed in particular depth in the context of Warburg’s madness. Didi-Huberman notes that during Warburg’s schizophrenic episode, under the care of Ludwig Binswanger, Warburg managed to transform his suffering into an interpretive tool (Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006). During his time in sanatoria, Warburg elaborated an understanding of the symptom that exceeded its medical connotations. Symptoms became visible expressions of internal tensions and unresolved conflicts, both individual and cultural. This understanding informed his analysis of images, which he treated as symptoms revealing underlying dynamics of history and psyche.

Didi-Huberman extends this insight by proposing that symptom-images enable a reading of history that acknowledges its fractures, discontinuities, and contradictions. Warburg thereby develops a conception of historical time as symptom, where the breaks and discontinuities of history manifest themselves in images:

« *Qu'est-ce qu'un symptôme du point de vue du temps historique? Il s'agira, dans le contexte que nous analysons, de la rythmicité particulière d'un événement de survie: effraction (émergence du Maintenant) et retour (émergence de l'Autre), entremêlés. En d'autres termes, ce sera la concomitance inattendue d'un revers et d'une répétition* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 169).

The symptom is thus no longer merely a sign of illness, but a fundamental structure of experience that permits a new reading of history through its impurities and contradictions (Didi-Huberman, 2006).

Central to both Warburg and Didi-Huberman is the figure of the Nymph, which embodies the moving body and becomes a paradigmatic symbol of the symptom-image: « *concept presque musical, mélodique et rythmique de pétrification* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 340). Warburg applied the *Pathosformel* especially to the choreographic intensity of Renaissance painting, and particularly to representations of dancing female figures known as Nymphs (Warburg, 2005). He observed how these figures conveyed complex emotions through their movements and gestures, functioning as a visual language that resonates with universal human affects. With her billowing drapery and floating hair, the Nymph becomes an emblem of the fusion between emotion and form. She encapsulates psychic energy and archaic memory, making visible the interaction between psyche and history. This motif exemplifies the way images can act as symptoms, revealing psychic and emotional states across time (Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006).

Warburg and Didi-Huberman thus offer a conception of representation that integrates *pathos* and temporality at a deep level. Through notions such as *Pathosformel* and the triad of phantom-image, pathos-image, and symptom-image, they challenge linear interpretations of art history and instead propose an ontology of historical time that is impure, discontinuous, and saturated with psychic meaning (Warburg, 2005; Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006). In this framework, images do not simply depict external reality; they also render visible « *l'inconscient de l'histoire* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 275), enabling a more profound and dynamic understanding of human experience. « *Les formules du pathos rendent visible non pas une qualité du monde extérieur mais un état affectif* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 281).

This approach not only transforms our understanding of art history but also furnishes tools for interpreting the complexity of emotional and psychic experience over time. Images, as moving fossils and cultural symptoms, reveal the constant interaction between past and present, offering a vision of art and history that is at once affective and intellectual: « *Il n'y a pas d'histoire possible sans histoire de la culture, il n'y a pas d'histoire de la culture sans histoire de l'art ouverte aux résonances anthropologiques et morphologiques des images* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 109).

In this section I have sought to foreground one particular aspect that shapes Didi-Huberman's interpretation of Aby Warburg: the triad phantom-image, pathos-image, and symptom-image. Although these three categories may be regarded as equivalent and their relations as unavoidably intermingled, I suggest that the symptom-image condenses—without univocally absorbing—the possibilities opened by the other two notions. In the symptom-image, discontinuous temporality becomes intelligible precisely through the phantasmagoria of the unconscious as a symptom of history. It is therefore possible to interpret the Nymph as the culmination and paradigm in which the three categories

converge, configuring the conceptual device that Didi-Huberman inherits from Warburg (Didi-Huberman, 2002, 2006).

As this analysis unfolds, the theory of the symptom-image is transformed into an experience of the symptom within Warburg's schizophrenia during his internment in Binswanger's clinic. For this reason, following Didi-Huberman, I have emphasised the period known as Aby Warburg's madness, for it is then that his theory of historical time as symptom crystallises. The symptom is no longer merely a sign of illness, « *mais plutôt comme une structure d'expérience fondamentale, l'instant éternel d'un être historiquement déterminé* » (Didi-Huberman, 2002, p. 379).

From this perspective, Warburg's work—as read by Didi-Huberman—not only offers a new understanding of art history beyond iconography and iconology but also proposes a reinterpretation of temporality itself, the raw material of historical inquiry. In a certain sense, when Warburg's science reaches its conceptual zenith in the symptom-image, it claims a place as a philosophical and interdisciplinary reading of the imaginal condition of a plural ontology of forms of being.

3. Representation between the One and the Multiple: Picasso in the Light of Luis Puelles' Aesthetic Theory

In *Mirar al que mira: Teoría estética y sujeto espectador*, Luis Puelles (2011) offers a crucial perspective for addressing the problem of representation. His analysis of the aesthetics of artistic contemplation is essential for understanding how the act of looking becomes central to the work of Pablo Picasso. Through aesthetic contemplation, one can better grasp how Picasso oscillates between the destruction and reconstruction of forms, between fragmentation and unification of the work, especially in the context of his rupture with traditional representation.

Puelles describes contemplation as an act that goes beyond mere superficial observation. This approach transcends simple seeing, becoming a bold exploration of the very nature of representation. The spectator (*spectare, aspectus, speculari*) attends to the act of the gaze, which

«no se agota en el momento... Starobinski nos recuerda que *regard* remite a estados bien significativos de la subjetividad del espectador: la espera, la consideración, el cuidado, la vigilancia. Sus palabras nos descubren a un espectador que no se limita a la simple constatación de existencia de su objeto de atención, siendo la suya una mirada moderna, en tanto que no solo afirma la continuidad de la apariencia en su estar ahí, sino que establece con “lo mirado” (que son los aspectos de su objeto) indefinidas relaciones de mayor tensión y complejidad» (Puelles, 2011, p. 134).

The spectator thus finds himself within what Puelles calls the “relación estética”:

«La relación estética precede y funda sus términos, entre los que se instituye una reciprocidad ontogenética. La obra artística y el receptor “se hacen correlativos” (se nacen o co-funden). Éste es el punto de vista de la hermenéutica: no es que el espectador sea y, además, se relacione. Es que su ser no es, de forma fundamental, sino estar en relación. Lo mismo le ocurre a la representación artística» (Puelles, 2011, p. 137).

This is precisely what Picasso's work invites: it compels the spectator to participate actively in the relational-participatory process of contemplation and in the free play of aesthetic offer and demand that constitutes representation. Picasso's gaze is not satisfied with evidences. His is a gaze in search of essence, of what lies latent beyond the surface. It is a suspicious gaze (*suspiciari*),

«que se pregunta por lo que ve y trasciende su inmanencia apariencial fascinante. Atiende a su existencia, pero, una vez que ésta queda constatada, entra en la consideración de sus cualidades, en la indagación de su naturaleza [...] inspecciona al sospechoso porque no le basta con lo que ve» (Puelles, 2011, pp. 134–135).

Puelles examines how the role of the spectator has evolved from the invention of Renaissance perspective to its decline in contemporary art. During the Renaissance, unified perspective afforded the spectator a coherent and stable vision of the world represented in painting. This conception persisted until Mannerism began to question these norms, introducing greater subjectivity into artistic perception:

«El Manierismo suprimirá el punto de fuga consiguiendo clausurar la profundidad de la imagen (la clausura es la condición imprescindible de la representación). Frente a la visión abierta al infinito (y pérdida o no retenida en la pintura misma: esa es la fuga -el ojo se fuga de la composición), la representación manierista cierra el cuadro, creando un espacio escenográfico y sólo ahora dramático» (Puelles, 2011, p. 152).

Puelles emphasises that the destruction of the vanishing point in Mannerism was a precursor of the modern subjectivity of the spectator:

«El siglo XVI promueve la supresión del punto de fuga de la perspectiva clásica, implicando esto la multiplicación de puntos de vista posibles. [...] El espectador es, a partir de esta multiplicación de posiciones, una subjetividad diferenciada» (Puelles, 2011, p. 153).

Picasso's work, especially with the development of Cubism, breaks with that unified Renaissance perspective and fragments reality into multiple viewpoints, demanding the spectator's active participation in order to be understood. Cubism challenged the foundations of Western representation which, since the Renaissance, had conceived painting as a window onto the visible world from a single vantage point. Picasso puts the traditional notion of representation into question by undermining established forms and creating new modes of seeing. When we look at a painting by Picasso, we enter into the relational-participatory free play of mutual gazes and interrogations.

This dynamic interaction between work and spectator, in the sense suggested by Puelles (2011), creates a contemplative space in which the unity of the act of looking reveals itself in all its complexity, challenging our assumptions about how images represent reality. To deepen this idea, consider the way Picasso uses space and form. In his cubist works, such as *Les Femmes d'Alger (O. J. R. M.)*, he decomposes figures and reintegrates them into a whole that challenges conventional perception. This technique not only questions two-dimensional representation but also the very notion of three-dimensionality, offering a new perspective that compels the spectator to reconstruct the image mentally. It is, in effect, a form of active contemplation: in contemplating a Picasso, we become co-creators of the work itself.

We must also consider the importance of fragmentation in Picasso's oeuvre as a means of achieving a deeper understanding of reality. Fragmentation in his work is not an end in itself but a pathway: a way of traversing the decomposition of reality into its essential elements in order, ultimately, to reconfigure it into a new unity, a new totality. This not only challenges linear perception but also traditional notions of representation. Such a process is not merely an aesthetic game; it is a way of accessing a deeper truth about the nature of reality and perception.

In this sense, Picasso's formal decomposition is not oriented towards destruction; it aims at expressing the intimate formality of essences on their way towards manifestation as a higher-order unity. The One and the Multiple are held in singular tension, encounter, metamorphic linkage. Contemplation here excludes any kind of passive gaze; it demands the spectator's active participation, who must mentally reconstruct forms and discern the underlying unity within apparent fragmentation.

Picasso thus ceaselessly challenges traditional perception and representation. The decomposition and reintegration of forms in his work not only undermine visual conventions but also invite the spectator to participate in a process of creation and discovery, questioning the very nature of what is seen.

In Cubism, the decomposition of perspective into multiple facets forces the spectator to reconstruct the image mentally, implying a heightened degree of interaction and participation. Following Puelles (2011), we can see how cubist theory fosters an active spectator, transformed from a passive observer into a dynamic participant in the artistic process. This is reflected in how Picasso and Braque drew on silent cinema as a catalyst to dismantle and then reconstruct the conventions of representation: shifting framings, cuts, and temporal discontinuities become analogues of the cubist fragmentation of space. The shattering of perspective in Cubism thus coincides with the necessity that the spectator become an integral part of the work.

Puelles (2011) also observes that the autonomy of artistic activity gives rise to the emergence of the expert as a new figure of reception. Picasso's work, especially in its more abstract and experimental phases, often seems to require expert interpretation to be fully appreciated. This reflects a tendency towards specialisation and a separation from mass art, where the work becomes self-referential and appears reserved for a more specialised public.

Although the action art of the 1960s marks a new phase in the disappearance of the traditional spectator, Picasso had already anticipated this shift with works that disrupted spectator passivity. The interaction required by Cubism and related movements prefigures the figure of the interactive user that Puelles associates with contemporary art. The disappearance of the traditional spectator gives rise to new modalities of receiver, such as the interactive user and the expert (Puelles, 2011).

Cubism marks the end of the nineteenth century in terms of the emergence of a new visuality and a new conception of the pictorial, but also in terms of the relations between artist, society, and market. Cubism makes it possible to explore the simultaneity of different viewpoints, generating a visual experience that questions conventional perception. The spectator's gaze in the cubist context is active creation: a reconstruction, as noted, of the One from the formal decomposition expressed in the Multiple. This decomposition of form represents a rupture with classical *mimesis*: representation is no longer mere imitation of reality, but the reconstruction of multiple realities into a new way of seeing.

In *Guernica*, Picasso uses fragmentation to capture the brutality and chaos of war. The decomposition of human and animal figures into angular, distorted forms registers the dehumanisation and violence of the conflict. This technique not only challenges the viewer's visual perception but also invites reflection on the nature of suffering and destruction. In *Guernica*, the disintegration of the human condition wrought by war is rendered through fragmentation.

It is also crucial to note the way in which the human face in Picasso's work acts as a mirror that reflects not only the identity of the represented subject but also that of the spectator. The face in Picasso functions as a reflection of the spectator's gaze, situated in a singular, onto-epistemological tension between identity and alterity. This play of reflections creates a contemplative dynamic in which the spectator becomes an integral part of the work, thereby calling into question the process of representation itself. Self-reflection and self-recognition: the use of the human face as a mirror in Picasso's work goes beyond revealing the identity of the spectator-subject. It is crucial for understanding the emotional and psychological depth of his oeuvre, where the act of contemplation becomes an introspective experience that challenges the norms of visual representation.

The analysis of Cubism reveals such complexity that, by 1911, its very geometric structure—conceived to clarify a new relation between world and subject—ends up dispensing with representation. Hermetic Cubism, as this new phase is called, is the step closest to abstraction. The multiple object gives way to a closed, difficult, and highly coded representation that presents the aesthetic field as a stage for the reinvention of another reality.

The influence of Cubism extends well beyond painting, affecting other arts such as poetry, dance, music, and theatre. The links between Orphism and literature, as well as the work of dancers like Loïe Fuller, exemplify the importance of these artistic forms for the development of the avant-garde language. In Spain, the painter María Blanchard shared this interest in movement, light, and colour during the central years of her work, confronting in her canvases the volumetric analysis of space characteristic of Cubism through faceting into planes and figurative decomposition.

Another fundamental aspect for understanding Picasso's challenge to the classical notion of representation is metamorphosis. Throughout his career, he played with the transformation of everyday objects into artistic forms, endowing them with new meanings and affects. Metamorphosis in Picasso can be read as a technique for auscultating the mutability of the real and the potential of art to transform the ordinary into the extraordinary. This process of transformation not only alters the appearance of the object but also invites the spectator to see beyond the surface, to explore the multiple facets of reality.

This capacity to metamorphose ordinary objects into artistic forms reflects Picasso's conception of representation as a dynamic, ever-evolving process. By transforming the ordinary into something extraordinary, he invites us to reconsider our relation to the surrounding world and to recognise the depth and complexity of reality.

In sum, Picasso's work not only challenges the traditional notion of representation; it also renders the spectator visible as an active component of the aesthetic experience. By fragmenting perspective and requiring the spectator's active participation, Picasso reflects the evolution of the spectator described by Puelles (2011), whereby the viewer becomes an indispensable participant in the creation and understanding of art. The cubist rupture with dominant pictorial conventions and the fragmentation of unified perspective exemplify how Picasso and his contemporaries redefined the relation between artwork and spectator, in tune with a dynamic, subjective modernity.

Cubism shows that experience is bound to reality and that, in modernity, reality is dynamic and subjective, irreconcilable with the static visual regime invented in the Renaissance. The connection between the cubist break and the aesthetics of artistic contemplation—as conceived by Puelles—thus provides a deeper understanding of the radical transformation that Cubism imposed on the perception and participation of the spectator in the work of art.

4. Conclusions

The theoretical proposals advanced by Jean-François Lyotard, Gilles Deleuze, Aby Warburg, Georges Didi-Huberman, and Luis Puelles challenge traditional notions of representation in Western art and aesthetics. Through an examination of their ideas, we have identified several ways in which artistic representation may be reconceived so as to disclose new dimensions of singularity, difference, immanent forces, and the active participation of the spectator.

Lyotard and Deleuze invite us to rethink representation from a perspective in which the figural and the sensorial destabilise the fixed structures of discourse and representation. Lyotard underscores the resistance of the figural to discursive subsumption, making visible the density of desire at work in the artwork. Deleuze, for his part, emphasises the sensorial forces that shape aesthetic experience, suggesting a dynamic interaction between the figurative and the abstract. Although their approaches diverge, they share a commitment to challenging inherited structures and to proposing an aesthetics that celebrates multiplicity and the irreducibility of sensorial and figural experience.

Warburg and Didi-Huberman offer a vision of representation that integrates pathos and temporality. Through concepts such as *Pathosformel*, *Nachleben*, and the triad of the phantom-image, the pathos-image, and the symptom-image, these thinkers propose an ontology of historical time that is impure, discontinuous, and saturated with psychic meaning. In this framework, images not only represent external reality but also render visible the unconscious of history, allowing for a deeper and more dynamic understanding of human experience. The figure of the Nymph emerges as a paradigmatic symbol that encapsulates these ideas, acting as a bridge between psyche and history.

Luis Puelles, in turn, provides a critical tool of immense value for analysing the work of Pablo Picasso and Cubism, emphasising the importance of aesthetic contemplation and the active participation of the spectator. An analysis of fragmentation and reintegration in Cubism reveals how Picasso challenges conventional perception and demands a dynamic form of engagement from the viewer. This aesthetic theory enables a more nuanced understanding of how Cubism and other forms of modern art transform the relationship between artwork and spectator, fostering active participation and the co-creation of meaning.

Taken together, these theoretical reflections underscore the importance of reconsidering traditional conceptions of representation in art and aesthetics. By questioning and destabilising established structures, these thinkers invite us to explore new modes of understanding and appreciating art—modes that value singularity, difference, and the active participation of the viewer. This approach not only enriches our comprehension of contemporary aesthetics but also provides a conceptual framework for addressing the complexities and internal dynamics of artistic representation in a cultural and political landscape in constant transformation.

Ultimately, these proposals lead us to recognise artistic representation as a field of cultural resistance and a space of creation that celebrates multiplicity and difference. Such a deepened understanding of artistic representation allows us to appreciate art not as an object of passive contemplation but as a dynamic and participatory process that challenges our habitual conceptions and enriches our aesthetic and cultural experience.

References

- Deleuze, G. (2002). *Logique de la sensation*. Seuil.
- Deleuze, G., & Guattari, F. (1972). *L'Anti-OEdipe*. Les Éditions de Minuit.
- Didi-Huberman, G. (2002). *L'image survivante: Histoire de l'art et temps des fantômes selon Aby Warburg*. Les Éditions de Minuit.
- Didi-Huberman, G. (2006). *Ante el tiempo*. Adriana Hidalgo Editora.
- Lyotard, J.-F. (1971). *Discours, figure*. Klincksieck.

- Puelles Romero, L. (2011). *Mirar al que mira: Teoría estética y sujeto espectador*. Abada Editores.
- Warburg, A. (2005). *El Renacimiento del paganismo: Aportaciones a la historia cultural del Renacimiento europeo*. Alianza Editorial.
- Warburg, A. (2023). *L'atlas Mnémosyne*. L'Ecarquillé.